

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE LOW ADOPTION RATE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCE IN SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on factors influencing the low adoption rate of RE in Southwestern Nigeria. The insufficient and erratic supply of electricity in Southwestern Nigeria, relative to its energy demand, has driven attention and interest in exploring alternative energies. The changing climate conditions, oil price fluctuations, and increasing environmental awareness have highlighted the importance of effective energy management systems in reducing greenhouse gases. These factors have made individuals and organisations seek other alternatives to obtain a regular supply of energy, which can only be efficiently obtained through the utilisation of renewable energy (RE). However, insufficient attention has been paid to the potential of RE resources in residential, commercial, and industrial applications. The goal of the study is to examine the factors influencing the low adoption rate of RE in Southwestern Nigeria. The paper first examines the renewable energy potential in the region before delving into those factors. The identified factors include a lack of investors and shareholders, economic and financial barriers, lack of modern infrastructures for the storage of RE, lack of training and workforce to initiate RE projects, technical barriers and poor quality products, low public awareness and sociocultural factors, policy and regulatory weakness, institutional and governance challenges and dependence on fossil fuels and generator economy. The paper concludes by looking at policy implications and ways to improve adoption rate.

Keywords: Renewable energy (RE), adoption rate, epileptic power supply.

1.0 Introduction

Nigeria is still grappling with erratic power supply without adequate access to reliable and affordable energy for socioeconomic development, despite being the most populous nation in Africa. Also, in spite of the abundant fossil fuels available in the country, the country's electricity generation capacity (Table 1) remains well below the needs of its population, with millions relying on expensive and polluting backup diesel generators to meet their energy needs (Adeyemi et al., 2024).

Table 1: Electricity Generating capacity in Nigeria (NERC, 2024)

Categories	Values
Installed Generation Capacity	Approximately 13, 000 MW
Available Generation Capacity	Approximately 4,000-6000 MW
Peak Generation	5000 MW
Transmission Capacity	8100 MW
Total Energy Consumption	Approximately 30,000 MW (this is the estimated national demand)

Energy, as one of the most basic necessities of humans, has continued to witness an increase in demand as technology advances (Balcioglu & Soyer, 2017). Globally, the emphasis is now on renewable energies for sustainability. While some developing countries have not made significant progress in adopting this energy in recent years, developed countries are increasing their usage of RE sources (Bent Sorensen, 1991). As a clean and inexhaustible energy source, RE has a major

role in reforming the present society (Güney, 2019; Oseni, 2012; Ayodele *et al.*, 2021; Akuru & Okoro, 2010; Chen and Lei, 2018). Nigeria is endowed with considerable RE potential, such as an average daily solar radiation of 3.5 to 7.0 kWh/m², abundant hydropower sites, and significant biomass and wind resources (Ugwu *et al.*, 2022). In spite of this potential, the country's total installed RE capacity stood at approximately 2,000 MW as of 2023 (IRENA, 2023).

RE is used to provide energy in wind turbine power plants, hydroelectric power plants, photovoltaic power systems, biomass systems, geothermal power plants for electricity generation, and rural energy services (Chow *et al.*, 2014). The capability of an energy source to be reformed entails that the harvesting, conversion and the utilization occurs in a sustainable way, hence evading negative impacts on the environment (Akuru & Okoro, 2010). Each of the RE sources (Figure 1) has unique features that influence how and where they are to be utilised (Akorede *et al.*, 2016). Stand-alone solar systems are now being deployed throughout the industrialized and developing world on a commercial scale, with the global market demand for PV exceeds 5 billion USD annually (Chudnovsky, 2017). The adoption of renewable sources is to solve the twin problems of electricity generation deficit and job creation (Adeniyi and Ige, 2024).

Figure 1: Renewable Energy Sources (Trivedi, 2024)

There are barriers to the adoption of the RE in Nigeria (Owen, 2006). Adebajji *et al* (2024) identified a low awareness and acceptability of RE in the Southwest part of Nigeria. Ogunyemi and Adetona (2020) also identified low awareness in the maintenance of solar in some parts of the Southwest, too. The region is noted for its commercial activity with a complex pattern of energy demand. This paper aims to identify those factors responsible for the low adoption of RE in the region. This study focuses mainly on the rationale behind the low level of RE adoption and acceptance in Southwestern Nigeria while exploring its potential in the region as well.

2.0 RE Resources in Southwestern Nigeria

Southwestern Nigeria lies within latitudes 6°N and 8°N and is characterised by a humid tropical climate, abundant rainfall, and perennial river systems, thus possessing RE potential due to this geographical location.

A country's access to electricity should be efficient and effective in order to maximise economic and social benefits (Demirbaş, 2006). There is a need, therefore, for domestic, commercial and industrial users of electricity to ensure the RE is efficiently adopted and utilised (Bull, 2001). RE has been identified as a good alternative source and solution for poor power supply in Nigeria (Oyedepo, 2014). Access to efficient electricity in Southwestern Nigeria comprising Lagos, Oyo,

Ondo, Ogun, Osun and Ekiti has been low with very poor power supply. The consequence of this is alternative power generation, which increases the cost of production with uncertainty in the business ecosystem (Ayodele *et al.*, 2021; Olanipekun and Adalakun, 2020; Oseni, 2012).

2.1 Solar Energy

Solar energy has been the oldest energy source, and until recently discovered that it could generate electrical power when material like selenium is exposed to sunlight (Taguchi *et al.*, 2019), (Awan and Khan, 2014). (Taguchi *et al.*, 2019). Solar energy is influenced by solar irradiance, and the solar panel efficiency has increased over time, making it more affordable, and the installation of the solar system continues to soar (Gao *et al.*, 2020; Reece, 2013). Unlike the northern part of the country that enjoyed more abundant sunshine, the southwest receives about 3.5 to 4.5kWh/m² of solar radiation, which is still commercially viable for photovoltaic applications (Ohunakin *et al.*, 2014; Akinola, 2023). However, there is huge gap in RE potential and present utilisation in Nigeria as a whole with the installed solar PV capacity of only about 112MW in 2023(Adeyemi *et al.*, 2024).

Figure 2: Solar irradiation data for Nigeria (Nwulu and Agboola, 2011)

For a typical residential off-grid solar PV system in Lagos (with a daily load of 5 kWh/day), Table 1 shows the summary of solar sizing.

Table 2: Typical Solar sizing parameters for a residential off-grid solar PV system in Southwestern Nigeria

Parameter	Formula / Value	SW Nigeria (Lagos)	Notes
Daily Energy Demand (E_a)	Load (kW) × hours/day	5.0 kWh/day	Typical medium-density household
PV Array Size (kWp)	$E_a / (PSH \times \eta_{stst})$	~1.47 kWp	$\eta_{stst} = 0.75$ (derating factor)
Battery Bank Capacity	$E_a \times DoA / DoD \times V_{nam}$	~133 Ah @ 48V	DoA=2 days, DoD=0.8

Charge Controller (MPPT)	$I_{sn} = PV \text{ Array (W)} / V_{namn}$	30–40 A	MPPT preferred over PWM
Inverter Rating	$1.25 \times \text{Peak Load}$	~1.5 kVA	25% surge allowance
Tilt Angle (Fixed)	$\theta = \text{latitude (approx.)}$	6° South-facing	For Lagos (6.5°N)
Performance Ratio (PR)	E_{ant} / E_{aino}	0.70–0.75	Degraded by heat & humidity

The energy yield (kWh/kWp/year) from solar PV systems in the southwest is estimated at approximately 1,500–1,650 kWh/kWp/year, compared to 1,900–2,100 kWh/kWp/year achievable in the North Central and Northwest zones (Njoku, 2014). The performance ratio (PR) in Southwestern Nigeria is further reduced by thermal losses, as module temperatures frequently exceed 50°C due to tropical ambient conditions. For every 1°C rise above the standard test condition (STC) of 25°C, crystalline silicon PV modules lose approximately 0.45% in efficiency (Awai *et al.*, 24).

In comparison with other parts of the country, Table 3 shows the average solar radiation in Nigeria.

Table 3: Comparative solar energy resource endowment across Nigerian geopolitical zones (NASA, 2023)

Zone	Average Solar Radiation (kWh/m ² /day)	Rating
North East	6.0-7.0	Excellent
North West	5.8-6.8	Excellent
North Central	5.5-6.2	Very High
South West	4.8-5.5	High
South South	4.2-5.0	Moderate
South East	4.3-5.1	Moderate

2.2 Hydroelectric Energy

This is harnessing the energy of rivers and streams to transform mechanical energy into electric energy through the hydro turbines (Demirbaş, 2006; Naghizadeh *et al.*, 2012). Hydropower is connected to a number of other services, including water storage, irrigation, and flood control. In order to operate effectively, the hydro sector must consider a variety of elements, including expected changes in river flows, dam safety, vulnerability, and climate change concerns (Nguyen *et al.*, 2019). In Nigeria, the potential for small hydropower is maximum in the southern region of the country, where rainfall is persistent with the availability of large rivers (Brimmo *et al.*, 2017). Due to its abundance and widespread availability of well-known technologies, hydropower energy has the greatest potential for development in rural or distant places with possibilities of jobs creation throughout the construction phase (Akorede *et al.*, 2016). However, there are also challenges associated with hydropower (Aliyu *et al.*, 2015; Abbasi and Abbasi, 2000).

Hydropower potential is characterised by the gross head (H) and the volumetric flow rate (Q) of a river or stream. The theoretical power output of a hydropower system is given by:

$$P \text{ (kW)} = \eta \times \rho \times g \times Q \times H \times 10^{-3}$$

Where: η = overall efficiency (typically 0.80–0.86 for modern Pelton/Kaplan turbines), ρ = density of water (1,000 kg/m³), g = gravitational acceleration (9.81 m/s²), Q = flow rate (m³/s), H = net head (m).

Nigeria’s large hydropower capacity is concentrated almost entirely in the North Central zone, where the Kainji (760 MW), Jebba (578 MW), and Shiroro (600 MW) dams account for the bulk of the national 2,100 MW installed capacity. The Southwest’s small hydropower potential, while modest by comparison, remains systematically underexploited. The hilly terrain of Ekiti and Ondo xStates is well-suited for micro and mini hydropower schemes (1–500 kW), which could serve as reliable, low-maintenance baseload power sources for rural communities without grid access.

Southwestern Nigeria is traversed by major river systems, including the Osun, Ogun, Owena, and Ero rivers (Table 4), offering modest but viable small hydropower potential. Though Nigeria’s total hydropower installed capacity stands at 2,100 MW nationally, yet the available sites in the southwest remain largely undeveloped (Adeyemi et al., 2024). Small and mini-hydropower projects hold particular promise for rural electrification in the hilly terrains of Ekiti and Ondo States.

Table 4: Small hydropower potential at key sites in Southwestern Nigeria (ECN, 2023)

Location	State	Estimated Potential
Ikere Gorge	Oyo	6 MW
Oyan Dam	Ogun	9 MW
Erinle River	Osun	3 MW
Owena River	Ondo	4 MW
Ero Dam	Ekiti	2MW

2.4 Wind Energy

The power available in the wind per unit swept area is given by:

$$P/A \text{ (W/m}^2\text{)} = 0.5 \times \rho_{\text{air}} \times v^3 \times C_p$$

Where $\rho_{\text{air}} \approx 1.15 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (tropical air density at 30°C), v = wind speed (m/s), and C_p = Betz coefficient (max 0.593). At a mean speed of 4.0 m/s, the theoretical wind power density is approximately 37 W/m². This is significantly below the 200 W/m² achievable at 7.0 m/s in northern zones. Wind energy in the southwest is therefore most viable for small-scale water pumping and hybrid (solar-wind) off-grid systems rather than utility-scale generation, and only in coastal and elevated terrain locations.

Wind energy in Southwestern Nigeria is severely constrained by the region’s low average wind speeds relative to the rest of the country. Sokoto State in the Northwest receives average annual wind speeds exceeding 7.0 m/s at hub height. By contrast, most inland southwestern sites average less than 4.0 m/s, yielding capacity factors below 12% that make standalone wind projects uneconomical at current turbine capital costs. With average speeds of 4.0–4.5 m/s at 10 m height and potentially 5.5–6.5 m/s at 80 m hub height, the coastal belt of Lagos and Ondo States presents the most viable wind sites in the Southwest.

For the near term, wind energy in the Southwest is best deployed in hybrid solar-wind micro-grid configurations where even modest wind resources can supplement solar generation during nighttime and overcast periods.

2.4 Biomass Energy

Biomass for bioenergy is derived directly from the land, such as from crops grown specifically for that purpose, or from leftovers left over after crops are processed for food or other products (Ellabban *et al.*, 2014; Sachdev, 2015). Compared to other energy sources, biomass energy is more

affordable to produce and provides adequate energy. The yearly global production of biomass is eight times higher than the annual global consumption of all other energy sources (Taylor *et al.*, 2006). Biomass differs from other energy forms on the basis of diversity, production and utilization of techniques in the overall energy production cycle for instance, dry and wet feedstock can be used to produce solid, liquid, and gaseous fuels.

As one of the first forms of energy used by humanity, a variety of energy needs are satisfied by biomass which includes the generation of electricity (Taylor *et al.*, 2006; Bildirici, 2012; Bishoge *et al.*, 2018). Because of the elimination of the green vegetation, land erosion is one of the effects of biomass energy on the environment (Mohtasham, 2015).

3.0 Factors Influencing Low Adoption Rate of RE in Southwestern Nigeria

Southwestern Nigeria has industrial establishments, houses, commercial businesses, tourist attractions and substantial population of people that requires constant electricity. The region is endowed with natural resources such as sunlight, rivers and streams, fossil fuel reserves (made from the decomposition of plants and animals), and wind (Bishoge *et al.*, 2018). The renewable energy resource scorecard by geopolitical zone is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Renewable energy resource scorecard by geopolitical zone (IRENA, 2023)

Zone	Solar	Hydro	Biomass	Wind	Overall
North East	5	2	3	4	14
North West	5	3	4	5	17
North Central	4	5	5	3	17
South West	4	3	5	2	14
South East	3	3	4	2	12
South South	3	1	5	1	10

The low adoption rate of RE technologies in Southwestern Nigeria is a function of many interacting factors. While beliefs and evaluations determine attitude, normative beliefs, and motivation determine norm. Behaviour is a function of intention, which is a product of attitude and norm (Akinwale and Adepoju, 2019). This section examines some of these major probable factors that can influence the low adoption of RE.

3.1 Lack of Investors and Shareholders

The lack of investors has a significant potential to influence the adoption of RE in Southwestern Nigeria. Typically, RE projects have a high initial cost for their infrastructure, which may put off investors seeking lower-risk opportunities. Uncertainty about the long-term financial returns can be a deterrent for potential investors with the investment status on RE lacking (Edu, 2021). Even where RE options exist, many potential users face challenges in securing financing due to high-interest rates or a lack of access to loans. Without affordable financing options, the high acquisition costs remain a significant deterrent. In many places, governments do not provide enough subsidies, tax credits, or incentives to reduce the initial costs of RE installations. Without these incentives, the cost of acquisition remains high, particularly in regions where the RE sector is not yet fully developed. Countries that do offer substantial incentives have seen higher adoption rates, as these policies make RE more accessible to the general public.

3.2 Economic and Financial Barriers

Adeniyi and Ige (2024) identified high acquisition cost as the main barrier to nationwide adoption of RE. The initial cost for implementing the renewable technology is usually high (Mbamalu, 2019). The purchase and installation of solar PV systems represent a significant financial burden for the majority of households in Southwestern Nigeria, especially low-income earners and rural dwellers (Adebanji et al., 2024). In such low-income areas, many will prioritise basic needs over long-term investments in RE. Addiction to cheap alternatives and less reliable but affordable fossil fuels with a lot of negative effects on the ecosystem is the main problem (Owen, 2006). Furthermore, RE technologies are imported, which is the leading factor of additional costs due to taxes, tariffs, and import duties. This is especially true in regions like Southwestern Nigeria without a strong domestic manufacturing base for RE equipment. Total dependence on the importation of renewable materials not only increases the acquisition cost but can also lead to supply chain issues which can discourage people.

Compounding this challenge is the limited access to financing. Unlike in more developed markets, where green mortgages, equipment leasing, and consumer credit facilities exist to spread the cost of RE systems, Nigerian households and small businesses face a financial sector that largely lacks dedicated RE lending products. Nigeria's inflation rate surged to 16 per cent in 2022, further curtailing capital availability and restricting developers' access to project financing (World Economic Forum, 2023). Currency fluctuations and the difficulty of obtaining foreign exchange at the official rate add further risk to import-dependent RE supply chains. Ugulu (2022) identifies high upfront cost and lack of finance as the principal barriers to urban solar energy adoption in Nigeria, noting that unreliable grid supply and potential cost savings from replacing generator use serve as the primary motivators for adoption when it does occur. In the absence of accessible financing, many households in Southwestern Nigeria fall back on short-term fossil fuel alternatives, particularly petrol and diesel generators, which are widely available but expensive and environmentally harmful.

3.3 Lack of Modern Infrastructures for the RE' Storage

The right infrastructure are needed to be put into place in order to fully harness the benefits of RE, and where such is lacking, it will hinder broader adoption of RE technologies. For instance, the need for specialised components and monitoring devices for maintenance and sustainability of the renewable system cannot be overemphasised. Also, RE sources like solar and wind, which are subject to intermittent power, require adequate storage solutions. This intermittency issue limits RE's effectiveness in providing reliable power without modern storage systems, such as batteries or pumped hydro storage, to balance supply and demand. In the same vein, modern energy storage is equally expensive. The high costs of these storage systems discourage wide-scale adoption and make RE projects less attractive to investors and consumers who seek affordable, reliable solutions. Without proper storage solutions, much of the energy produced by renewable sources can go unused. For example, during peak sunlight hours, solar panels may generate more power than needed, and without storage, the excess energy is wasted. This wastage can discourage investment in RE systems since it reduces the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of the installation, especially in places where grid-connected storage or individual storage options are unavailable (Owen, 2006).

3.4 Lack of Training and Skill Workforce to Initiate RE Projects

RE is recent, and as a result, they require a high skilled workforce to be able to follow the development of the RE technologies from their initial planning to the final installation of parts. This will affect the installation and sustainability of RE, where the availability of such trained personnel is limited. RE projects, such as solar, wind, hydro and bioenergy installations, require specialised technical skills for design, installation, operation, and maintenance. In many regions, especially in developing countries like Nigeria, there is a shortage of professionals trained in these specific areas, which hampers project initiation and sustainability.

Without sufficient technical expertise, projects may not be executed to optimal standards, leading to inefficiencies, higher costs, and even failures, which in turn erode confidence in RE. Skilled workers are essential for understanding and adapting technologies to local conditions, innovating solutions to unique regional issues, and ensuring that projects are optimised for efficiency.

Lack of skilled labour limits the potential for technological advancements within the region, stifling innovation and local industry growth within the RE sector.

A scarcity of trained technicians and engineers capable of installing, maintaining, and repairing RE systems in Southwestern Nigerian communities creates further adoption friction. Without accessible after-sales service networks, system failures deter repeat purchases and referrals. Nigeria's broader challenge of inadequate infrastructure, such as weak transmission and distribution networks, limits the ability to integrate off-grid renewable systems into hybrid grid arrangements, undermining the commercial viability of scale-up (Adeyemi et al., 2024).

3.5 Technical barriers and Poor quality Products and Services

Technical barriers constitute a significant dimension of the low adoption challenge. The quality and reliability of RE products and services available in Nigerian markets have been subjects of consumer concern, particularly with respect to substandard solar panels and inverters that enter the market through informal trade channels. Poor product quality has damaged consumer confidence and reinforced scepticism about the durability of RE technologies (Akinola, 2023). Poor installations have equally eroded many customers' confidence in solar due to financial losses experienced. Research has also identified the limited scope of energy generated by household solar systems as a key constraint on willingness to transition away from grid power and generator combinations (Anugwom et al., 2020).

3.6 Low Public Awareness and Sociocultural Factors

A recurring finding across studies of RE adoption in Southwestern Nigeria is the very low level of public awareness regarding the nature, benefits, operational characteristics, and long-term cost-effectiveness of RE technologies. Research conducted across the six states of Southwestern Nigeria revealed a very low level of awareness and acceptability of RES among household consumers, rural dwellers, and even some policymakers (Adebanji et al., 2023; Ogunyemi and Adetona, 2020). Many respondents are uninformed about the environmental benefits, energy independence, and cost savings associated with solar, wind, and biomass systems.

The phenomenon of fuel stacking, in which households maintain multiple energy sources simultaneously, reflects both risk aversion and limited confidence in the reliability of new technologies. A study of Solar Home Systems (SHS) adoption in southeastern Nigeria found that over 75% of respondents ranked SHS as the last choice of household energy source, with none selecting it as the primary option (Anugwom et al., 2020). Adoption was shown to be strongly influenced by concerns about system reliability and the limited energy output generated, rather

than by socioeconomic status per se. Social norms, limited peer demonstration effects, and community trust deficits in new technology suppliers also play a role. In the absence of community champions and trusted local distributors of RE systems, prospective adopters in Southwestern Nigeria face informational barriers that formal marketing alone has proven insufficient to overcome. The need for a societal mindset shift and multi-stakeholder education campaigns has been widely acknowledged as an essential prerequisite for improved adoption (World Economic Forum, 2023).

3.7 Policy and Regulatory Weaknesses

A number of policies aimed at promoting RE development are already in place in Nigeria. This includes the National RE and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP), the 2023 Power Sector Reform Bill and the RE Master Plan (REMP). Through the enactment of the 2023 Electricity Bill, States, private organisations, and individuals can now participate in electricity generation, transmission and distribution (World Economic Forum, 2023). However, due to a lack of coherence and alignment, the frameworks are yet to yield meaningful gains in adoption rates.

A primary challenge is the inadequacy and inconsistency of existing legal frameworks, as policies frequently operate in isolation without alignment to broader energy sector regulations. The target of the RE Master Plan is to increase the share of RE in the national energy mix. However, due to overlapping mandates, poor enforcement mechanisms, and the absence of a comprehensive integrated RE law, the implementation progress has been very slow.

Hampering project development are factors such as a lack of must-run status for renewables in power dispatch protocols, restrictive power purchase agreements, and complex permits. With the absence of clear policy signals, investors face an uncertain environment that discourages long-term commitment to RE projects in the region. Also, net metering regulations and feed-in tariff mechanisms that have facilitated RE uptake in other jurisdictions remain underdeveloped in Nigeria.

3.8 Institutional and Governance Challenges

The institutional landscape governing RE in Nigeria is characterised by fragmentation and poor inter-agency coordination. As noted previously, key bodies, including the Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN), the Rural Electrification Agency (REA), the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC), and the Ministry of Power, have overlapping mandates that frequently generate administrative delays and inefficiencies. This fragmentation weakens the coherent delivery of incentive programmes, electrification projects, and market development initiatives that would otherwise stimulate RE adoption in Southwestern Nigeria. Corruption and bureaucratic inefficiency further exacerbate these institutional challenges, making it difficult for RE projects to progress through permitting, grid connection, and off-take agreement processes. Though agencies like REA are making efforts, this remains a fraction of what is required, given the scale of energy poverty in the country.

3.9 Dependence on Fossil Fuels and the Generator Economy

As the most populous nation in Africa, with over 80% of power generation historically derived from gas reserves, Nigeria remains the largest consumer of alternative backup generators in Africa (World Economic Forum, 2023). Southwestern Nigeria, particularly the Lagos megacity, is home to one of the world's highest concentrations of backup diesel and petrol generators per capita. This

generator-driven economy created a complex chain of well-organised informal energy industry with vested interests in maintaining fossil fuel dependence.

In Southwestern Nigeria, like the rest of the country, the so called standby generator has become a defacto main source while the public power supply serves as an alternative. Despite its high operating cost, noise, carbon emissions, and health hazards, it has become the immediate and available energy solution. The huge cost of initial investment in RE is hindering many to take advantage of it. This lock-in effect reinforces the need for financial instruments that specifically target generator replacement as a pathway into RE adoption.

4.0 The Way Forward

The analysis presented above reveals that no single barrier is solely responsible for the low adoption rate of RE in Southwestern Nigeria. Rather, these barriers constitute an interlocking system in which each weakness reinforces others: lack of financing reduces market development; a small market fails to attract quality suppliers; poor product quality erodes consumer confidence; low consumer confidence weakens political pressure for policy reform; and weak policy environments deter institutional investors. Breaking this cycle requires interventions that simultaneously address multiple dimensions.

Financial sector development is perhaps the most immediately tractable lever. The introduction of dedicated RE consumer finance products would materially reduce the barrier of high upfront costs for households and small enterprises in Southwestern Nigeria. The REA's Solar Power Naija Programme has demonstrated a model for government-facilitated market development that could be scaled regionally (World Economic Forum, 2023).

Policy coherence and enforcement represent an equally urgent priority. The formulation of an integrated regional RE law for Southwestern Nigeria's state governments, aligned with the federal NREEEP and REMP frameworks, would provide clearer investment signals and reduce regulatory uncertainty. The adoption of feed-in tariff mechanisms, net metering regulations, and mandatory RE content standards for new commercial and residential buildings in Lagos, Ibadan, and other major cities would catalyse adoption at scale.

Institutional capacity building across ECN, NERC, REA, and state-level energy agencies is essential to improve project appraisal, approval, and monitoring efficiency. Reducing bureaucratic delays, streamlining permitting processes, and establishing single-window approval mechanisms for RE installations would significantly lower transaction costs for project developers and household adopters alike.

Public awareness campaigns, particularly those leveraging community radio, social media, and demonstration projects at schools, markets, and community centres across the six southwestern states, are needed to shift societal perceptions of RE from unfamiliar technology to a trusted and desirable solution. Partnerships between government, civil society, and the private sector are critical to designing culturally appropriate communication strategies (World Economic Forum, 2023).

5.0 Conclusion

This paper has examined the multidimensional factors responsible for the persistently low adoption rate of RE technologies in Southwestern Nigeria. Southwestern Nigeria, with its significant and largely untapped solar, small hydropower, and biomass resources, possesses the potential to achieve a substantial transformation of its energy mix if targeted and coordinated interventions are implemented. The window of opportunity is significant: rapid urban growth,

increasing energy costs, growing environmental awareness, and expanding global supply chains for affordable RE technologies collectively create enabling conditions for accelerated adoption.

Realising this potential will require sustained commitment from federal and state governments, development finance institutions, private sector actors, civil society organisations, and research institutions working in concert. Future research should focus on granular, state-level demand assessments, the design and evaluation of innovative financing models suited to Southwestern Nigeria's socioeconomic conditions, and the development of culturally tailored behaviour change strategies for RE adoption.

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